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LONG TERM EARTH OBSERVATION MARKET DEVELOPMENT OF ENVISAT-BASED SERVICES

LINE 4: Environmental Information for Marine Operations

ENVISAT MONITORING AND FORECASTING SERVICES FOR OFFSHORE INDUSTRY (EMOFOR)

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1. EMOFOR SERVICE OBJECTIVES AND BACKGROUND

1.1 OBJECTIVES

The main goal of this longer-term market development study is to develop environmental information services for marine operations associated with the offshore oil and gas industry. The service will in the first phase be focused on a segment of this market, floating construction in deep water. In the second phase the market will be expanded to the whole offshore sector. EO-data has started to be used as part of the service to the offshore industry by providing high resolution sea surface information such as sea surface height, sea surface waves, sea ice conditions etc. Real time sub sea information, such as current, temperature and salinity vertical profiles are obtained from sensors positioned on offshore facilities. Three-dimensional time series of high resolution oceanographic fields, such as current, temperature and salinity, can be provided by state of the art ocean circulation models, and used for the statistical estimation of design criteria. and design of an optimal future ocean monitoring and forecast service system for this market.

An optimal approach to creating an overall ocean monitoring and forecasting system is the integrated use of ocean models combined with observations of physical variables. This integration is done using data assimilation techniques, which provide a framework for the optimal combination of the information from the observations and the mathematical models. Satellite remote sensing of the sea surface is currently the main source of data for assimilation into ocean modelling systems. The satellite provides data such as sea surface temperature, sea level anomalies and ocean colour. However, the sub-surface and deep ocean cannot be observed directly by satellite remote sensing techniques, since electromagnetic waves are rapidly damped out in water and surface variables cannot be confidently extrapolated to depth. It is therefore essential to supplement the EO monitoring with in situ measurements and ocean modelling. Ocean modelling also makes it possible to integrate forward in time and thereby provide environmental forecasts.

The study will address the whole EO supply chain from data providers, value-adding companies, market owners to strategic customers, with focus on selected services where EO data from ENVISAT are expected to be of importance for the offshore industry market. The three following objectives will be achieved in the proposed study through joint effort of a consortium consisting of NERSC, CLS and Fugro GEOS:

- *Integrate EO-based services from NERSC, CLS and other leading VACs into the existing portfolios of geo-information provided by Fugro GEOS, who have the role as MO for environmental information for the offshore industry;*
- *Gain market acceptance of the offshore industry and grow commercial sales of EO-based information, using ENVISAT and other satellite data integrated with model simulations and in situ data;*
- *Develop relationships within the EO supply chain to improve it's functioning for international and global markets (as opposed to local or national markets) in order to support offshore operations worldwide.*

In this document the EMOFOR services are defined based on requirements from marine operators requirements for met-ocean information.

1.2 BACKGROUND

The services planned for development in EMOFOR are based on several years of development in operational oceanography. A driving organisation for operational oceanography in Europe is EuroGOOS (European Global Ocean Observation System), which is an association of agencies founded in 1994 for development of ocean monitoring and forecasting services. EuroGOOS is part of GOOS, developing global system for observations, modelling and analysis of marine and ocean variables to support operational ocean services worldwide.. The goals of EuroGOOS are:

- *to build on Scientific Success (integration of present skills into global and regional modelling, with forecasting, will provide a new range of profitable services);*
- *to create a new Operational Marine Services. (Operational oceanography will create new businesses and new jobs in Europe by providing predictions and forecasts, which will improve the efficiency of industries and services).*
- *to develop a Global System (The public expects a collaborative scientific approach to planetary environmental management. To succeed, we must learn to predict the ocean and coastal seas. European collaboration will permit Europe to wield influence on a global scale).*

Numerous sectors of the growing business of operational oceanography have been identified, and Members have compiled lists of hundreds of potential customers in each country. Many of the data and forecasts obtained by European and Government agencies will be processed further by commercial companies in the value-added industry, and transmitted through a chain of intermediaries to customer groups requiring very different products. The final benefits accrue within individual industries and activities such as Offshore oil and gas; Fisheries; Mineral extraction Defence, Pollution management; Climate prediction; Port operations; Coastal protection; Ship-routing; Aquaculture; Tourism; Public health.

Operational ocean forecasting systems rely on an integrated use of observations of physical, biological, and chemical variables and coupled physical and marine ecosystem models. These observations and the model dynamics are integrated using so called data assimilation techniques. These are mathematical techniques, which are usually based on some prior statistical assumptions about the accuracy of the observations and dynamical models. Essentially, these techniques provide a means for introducing the information about the true ocean-state into the models, hence limiting the model drift away from the real state of the ocean.

The provision of observational data, both satellite and in-situ based, and their integration into appropriate models of the Earth system are of paramount importance for monitoring the state of the environment and the climate, as required by national and international programs, obligations and treaties. Well documented examples are ozone depletion, atmospheric chemistry and transport of pollutants, El Nino Southern Oscillation, sea level and global ocean circulation, Arctic sea ice cover, and ice sheet elevation. In addition, the products and services delivered from numerical weather prediction centres, as well as from the growing number of operational and pre-operational oceanographic monitoring and modelling systems, all require access to integrated data systems. This integrated approach is a response to the marine operators' requirements for met-ocean services (described in chapter 2) and the basis for the EMOFOR services (described in chapter 3 - 5).

2. MARINE OPERATORS' REQUIREMENTS FOR MET-OCEAN SERVICES

2.1 COMMERCIAL MARKET

2.1.1 Target Market

The primary target market for the EMOFOR project is the offshore oil and gas industry, although it is recognised that there are other potentially exploitable markets, such as the military, that would utilise EMOFOR products. This sector is a major consumer of marine environmental information, and relies heavily on monitoring, forecasting and statistical data for safe and effective operations.

Use of EO information integrated with oceanographic data is limited within the offshore sector, but recent trends within the industry show the potential for growth is large. As shallow water oil reserves continue to dwindle and demand for hydrocarbons increases, deepwater reserves are becoming increasingly important to oil companies and indeed to individual nations. Up to 44% of reserves with development potential in the key areas of Brazil, Norway, West Africa, UK and the U.S. Gulf of Mexico lie in deepwater. The definition of 'deepwater' varies from region to region and from company to company, but in general refers to water depths exceeding 400m.

Oceanographically, shallow and deepwater oilfields are generally subject to different processes. On the continental shelf, tidal currents, wind-induced circulation, river runoff and (to a much lesser extent) ice melt are regionally-dependent key elements of the circulation. In deep water, however, where operations are more sensitive to environmental conditions, the spatial and temporal scales of oceanographic processes are more variable and often more severe; currents acting over several hundred metres of water can exert forces on offshore structures that are significantly greater than their shallow water counterparts. The increased variability, lower predictability and often more severe nature of deepwater circulation, means that measurements, monitoring and prediction of currents are of much greater importance than in the shallow water environment (Fig. 1). Therefore, operations in deep water require information of the current in four dimensions, including time, which demonstrates the importance of an integrated ocean monitoring and forecasting system using in situ measurements, remote sensing and modelling techniques.

The EMOFOR project aims to provide the offshore oil and gas industry with a comprehensive and flexible service that will enable operators to maximise safety and efficiency in harsh and sometimes hostile environments. The scales of physical variability, especially in the deepwater environment, are such that a combination of data sources is required to best achieve this aim. Table 1 summarises the sources of oceanographic data in the proposed EMOFOR service to the target market.

Table 1: Principal data sources for services to deepwater offshore operations

Data Source	Pros/cons	Mode of Usage
In-situ measurement	Long time series; relatively expensive; site specific.	Historic; real-time
Models	Good spatial coverage; Require careful validation against observed data; computationally intensive	Hindcast; forecast
EO-based data	Good spatial coverage; temporal resolution sometimes an issue	Historic; real-time. Products used in forecast mode.

In practice the offshore industry is best served by an integration of information from all three sources: in situ measurements, models and EO-based data.

Figure 1. Ocean current profile data are important for offshore operations using floating platforms

2.1.2 Applications of the EMOFOR Service to the Offshore Industry

The lifecycle of an offshore oil or gas field comprises several key stages. Each has specific requirements for oceanographic information, which traditionally has been derived more from in-situ observations and/or models, but is increasingly utilising EO-based information. Table 2 summarises the lifecycle phases and associated data requirements.

Table 2. Requirements for current data during the lifecycle of an offshore hydrocarbon field

Life Cycle Phase	Description	Data Requirements
Geophysical Exploration	Initial identification of possible sub-sea hydrocarbon reserves comes from seismic and geophysical survey. This is ship-borne and hence is subject to ambient oceanographic and meteorological processes.	(i) Knowledge of near-surface tidal and non-tidal currents prior to and during the survey is essential for accurate data retrieval from seismic arrays. In-situ measurements and models (real-time and historical) are primary sources for this information. (ii) Identification of strong oceanic features prior to and during the operation. Such features are often associated with elevated current speeds and may have signatures detectable by EO sensors.
Exploration/ Appraisal/ Drilling	After positive seismic results, exploratory drilling takes place to define the potential reservoir. If oil/gas is found appraisal wells are drilled to determine the extent and nature of the recoverable hydrocarbon reserves. In both cases, the drilling apparatus selected for a particular area must be safely operable in the conditions expected there and hence knowledge of ambient conditions is necessary.	(i) Real-time knowledge of near-surface tidal and non-tidal currents is necessary during the manoeuvring of the drilling rig. In-situ measurements and models are primary sources for this information. (ii) In dynamically active regions, EO-based information will assist with advance warning of oceanographic features associated with elevated current speeds, minimising downtime and enhancing safety.
Engineering Design	The design of the facilities, pipelines and hydrocarbon recovery processes requires detailed knowledge of expected oceanographic conditions, including estimates of extreme events for loading computations and of ambient operating conditions for fatigue and lifetime assessment.	Long time series of data are required for extreme value analysis and for the derivation of operational/fatigue statistics. Models are now regularly developed to provide such data, but EO-based information constitutes a highly useful corroborative data source.
Installation and Production	Offshore production facilities are towed out to the field, and sometimes across oceans from construction yards or other fields. The type of production facilities used (fixed, tethered or floating) will depend upon many issues, including water depth and general environment. The hydrocarbons may be exported directly from the field via shuttle tanker or shore pipeline, or the field may be tied back to an existing nearby facility. Structural integrity assessment is ongoing throughout the life of the field, and will be a particularly significant issue for the modern 'floater' technology being utilised in deep water regions.	(i) Tow-out and installation of offshore production facilities requires advance and real-time knowledge of oceanographic conditions, especially in regions of high dynamic variability. Model and in-situ measurements, combined with EO-based data, comprise an effective and comprehensive package. (ii) Forecasts of severe current events during hydrocarbon production would also mitigate downtime and enhance safety. Causative oceanic features may have signatures detectable by EO sensors, which can also be used to identify and track oil spills. Models also will in the future be used to provide forecasts of current conditions. (iii) Current variability (e.g. inter-annual, seasonal and high frequency) and the occurrence frequency of significant anomalous processes are key issues for structural fatigue analyses. Model data assimilated with EO-based information are particularly useful.
De-	Once the production phase is complete	Forecasts of extreme current events and a continuous

commissioning/ abandonment	the offshore structure is normally removed from the site and the well(s) abandoned.	assessment of local conditions is required. As in previous phases, both EO-based and more the more traditional data sources are essential.
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2.1.3 Client Base

The diversity of activities associated with the offshore oil and gas industry has led to a range of companies that would benefit from the EMOFOR service, which must therefore be sufficiently flexible to meet the individual needs of the various sector components. Essentially, there are two groups of EMOFOR clients:

- (i) Offshore service recipients - primarily oil companies, organisations in this category receive contractor services, including those proposed by the EMOFOR consortium. Although many oil companies function globally (see below), each operational region may be assumed to be independent and hence each may be treated as a potential recipient of EMOFOR services. The current trend for oil company mergers has prompted the emergence of smaller independent companies, who rely more heavily on contracted services.
- (ii) Offshore service providers – organisations that provide services to the recipient oil companies. Category sectors include seismic survey, geological studies, seabed mapping, pipeline deployment, ocean towage, heavy lift specialists, shipping, oil spill monitoring and environmental impact assessment. In some instances, the EMOFOR products would be obtained by oil companies and passed on to the contractors and hence although an important potential source of EMOFOR clients, this category is regarded as secondary to the offshore service recipients.

2.2 PRINCIPAL REGIONS OF INDUSTRY ACTIVITY

The offshore oil and gas industry operates globally, but several key regions have emerged as containing significant viable hydrocarbon reserves. These are Brazil, Northwest Europe (including Norway and United Kingdom Waters), the US Gulf of Mexico and West Africa. Secondary regions include Australia, the Caspian Sea, Gulf of Oman, India, the Mediterranean, Northwest Africa and the South China Sea. In addition, secondary areas that would benefit from ice monitoring include Alaska, eastern Canada, Sea of Okhotsk, the Barents Sea and the northern Caspian Sea.

To emphasise the applicability of the EMOFOR service to the needs of the offshore industry, descriptions of the major hydrocarbon-bearing regions are given below together with brief summaries of key oceanographic processes of note. The secondary regions given above are also an important potential source of revenue for the EMOFOR service.

2.2.1 Brazil

Brazil's considerable offshore reserves lie in four major regions, the Campos/Santos Basin in the south, Reconcavo, Potiguar and the Amazon Delta in the north. Of these, up to 70% are in deep

water¹. Until recently, the state-owned company Petrobras had a monopoly in the region, but other companies such as ChevronTexaco, bp Exploration, Shell and ExxonMobil now have interests there. The Roncador field in the Campos Basin is, at depths between 1400 and 1900m, one of the deepest exploration areas in the world.

The Brazilian coastline covers some 45° of latitude and the adjacent Atlantic waters are subject to a range of significant oceanographic processes. In the northern section the North Brazil Current, a major oceanic current flowing northwest along the coast, turns offshore at about 8°N shedding large warm-core eddies of 200km diameter. The eddies move northwest along the Brazilian coast and into the Caribbean where they disintegrate after a lifetime of around 100 days. The features are of concern to the offshore industry around Trinidad due to the high current speeds (~0.8 ms⁻¹ near-surface) associated with them. They influence currents through a large part of the water column and speeds can exceed 0.3ms⁻¹ at 900m depth². The North Brazil Current itself reaches a maximum strength (up to 2.0ms⁻¹) off the Amazon, whose outflow can induce significant currents considerable distances offshore.

Along the southern part of the Brazilian coast, the southward Brazil Current is subject to meandering and instabilities that may generate mesoscale eddies in the offshore regions. In the Campos Basin, surface currents exceeding 1.0ms⁻¹ have been measured, but a key feature of this region is the vertical structure of the water column. Layered water masses flow poleward and equatorward through the region, inducing significant shear that is of concern to deepwater operators.

2.2.2 Northwest Europe

The now mature North Sea province has dominated offshore activities in Northwest Europe, and although the focus here is switching to the development of marginal fields, substantial finds continue to occur. However, interest (from companies such as BP Exploration, ChevronTexaco, ExxonMobil, Enterprise, Shell, Phillips, Statoil, TotalFinaElf and Marathon) now also lies in the deepwater provinces along the European continental slope, from the west of the Ireland to northern Norway and including the deepwater area off the Faroe Islands. Collectively, these regions are known as the Atlantic Margin.

The Atlantic Margin experiences some of the harshest environmental conditions in the world, and exploitation of bp Exploration's now operational fields on the Scottish slopes west of the Shetland Islands has necessitated the development of new technology to cope with the conditions. Currents are of particular concern: the persistent slope current, which flows northward along the length of the continental slope, can exceed 1.5 ms⁻¹ in the Faroe-Shetland Channel; complex instabilities in the slope current can generate mesoscale eddies of 50km diameter and large scale meanders with speeds in excess of 0.75ms⁻¹. In Norwegian waters, interaction between the coastal and oceanic currents can also initiate eddy formation. Significant effort has already been devoted to developing a state-of-the-art numerical model of the wider Atlantic Margin (funded by NWAG, the Northwest

¹ Douglas-Westwood Associates, 1997. The World Deepwater report, 1998-2002

² W.E. Johns et al, 1990. The North Brazil Current retroflection: seasonal structure and eddy variability. J. Geophys. Res., **95**, C12, 22103-22120.

Approaches Group of oil companies), and the region has been the subject of several research projects that combined in-situ and EO-based information.

2.2.3 U.S. Gulf of Mexico

The Gulf of Mexico produces at least 25% of the total U.S crude oil output, and 33% of the natural gas³. The percentage of Gulf deepwater (>350m) oil production has increased from less than 5% in 1990 to more than 50% of the Gulf crude production, a trend that is set to continue. By 2000, there were more than 110 deepwater discoveries, two of which are in water exceeding 2000m in depth. There are more than 150 oil exploration and production companies active in the Gulf. The deeper regions have been dominated by the oil majors (bp Exploration, Shell, ExxonMobil etc), while the smaller independents have tended to restrict their activities to shallower waters. However, the recent trend of major-mergers will allow the smaller operators a foothold in deep water as the larger companies reduce their field portfolios. Field exploitation in such depths has resulted in the development of a range of production facility concepts, especially tension-leg and SPAR platforms, and legislation is expected to open the way to the use of Floating, Production, Storage and Offloading (FPSO) systems.

Although environmental conditions are generally benign, circulation in the Gulf is highly complex with numerous physical processes of great concern to the offshore industry. Large warm-core eddies of 300km diameter shed by the Loop Current (Fig. 2) have a life span of several months and move slowly west, and are detectable to depths of 800m and may be associated with surface currents of up to 2.0ms^{-1} . Sub-surface jets in excess of 2.0ms^{-1} have been observed over the continental slope at depths between 150m and 500m. Intensification of the flow near the seabed has been observed in water of 2000m, with speeds exceeding 0.75ms^{-1} at 100m above bed. Energetic atmospheric events such as hurricanes can induce flows of over 1.0ms^{-1} in the upper layers of the water column.

a)

b)

Figure 2. a) Map of ocean currents and the Loop Current in the Gulf of Mexico, b) example

³ American Petroleum Institute, 2001. Meeting the Environmental Challenge: Oil and Natural Gas Operations in the Gulf of Mexico. Internet document.

of current simulations by the Colorado University Princeton Ocean Model (CUPOM)

2.2.4 West Africa

The West African oil reserves comprise what is possibly the most exciting offshore prospect in the world, with potential reserves exceeding even those of the Gulf of Mexico and twice those of the Brazil discoveries. It is possible that by 2015 West Africa will provide up to 25% of the total U.S. oil imports. The majority of the prospects lie in the Gulf of Guinea, with Nigeria and Angola sharing more than 80% of the total West African offshore reserves⁴. The Congo has 5%, Cameroon and Equatorial Guinea 3% and Ivory Coast, Gabon and Ghana 2%. Active majors include TotalFinaElf, ChevronTexaco, ExxonMobil and Shell, with other independents aligning themselves for the marginal or mature prospects and those belonging to the second tier West African nations. Exploration is predicted to move eventually out from the 500-2000m water depth range to ultra-deep abyssal regions in depths up to 4000m.

The relatively benign environment and the extreme water depths of many of the reserves mean that floating production concepts are becoming increasingly common in the West Africa region, and hence the current and circulatory regimes through the water column are of critical importance to the operators. Oceanic currents dominate the circulation, although the large rivers draining into the Guinea Basin create significant local effects. Instability and filamentation in the cold Benguela Current flowing north along the coastal upwelling zone of Namibia and Angola may cause mesoscale eddies to detach and move north and west into the Atlantic Ocean. Experience with these features elsewhere suggests that they may be of concern to deepwater operators in Angolan fields such as Girassol and Dalia. Strong inertial currents set up by the wind fields are also evident in measurements in the southern part of the region.

2.3 SUMMARY OF OFFSHORE OPERATOR REQUIREMENTS

Table 3 summarises the main oceanographic features of each of the major hydrocarbon regions (the list is not exhaustive), and gives the principal EMOFOR components that would best resolve the processes.

Table 3. Summary of main oceanographic processes and primary EMOFOR components

Region	Process/feature	Primary EMOFOR components
Brazil/Trinidad	Retroflexion rings Vertical current shear Amazon outflow Solitons?	EO data; in-situ measurements Modelling; in-situ measurements In-situ measurements; EO data; modelling EO data; in-situ measurements
West Africa	Mesoscale eddies River inputs Inertial currents	EO data; modelling; in-situ measurements In-situ measurements; EO data; modelling In-situ measurements
Northwest Europe	Mesoscale eddies & meanders Slope current intensification	EO data; modelling; in-situ measurements Modelling; in-situ measurements
Gulf of Mexico	Loop Current eddies	EO data; modelling; in-situ measurements

⁴ Douglas-Westward Associates, 2001. Offshore West Africa: Looking beyond the limelight. Internet presentation.

	Near bed intensification Sub-surface jets	In-situ measurements; modelling In-situ measurements; modelling
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3. THE CONCEPT OF INTEGRATED MONITORING AND FORECASTING SERVICES

A general service chain providing oceanographical information to offshore industry operating in deep waters is shown in Figure 3. The service chain starts with the various input data: a) atmospheric forcing data used to drive ocean models, b) in situ oceanographical data from moorings, rigs, buoys or ships, and c) satellite data. Integrated service means that all these three categories of input data are used in the service chain. Furthermore, modelling systems are used in combination with observed data to provide optimal monitoring, hindcasting and forecasting services. This is concept A which represents a fully integrated service providing all important met-ocean information for marine operators. Such integrated service is innovative and has not yet been provided to the offshore market although there is demand for it. Figure 13 also show a more traditional service concept (concept B) where satellite data are used as the main data source. The EMOFOR service will include both concepts.

3.1. EO DATA OF RELEVANCE FOR THE SERVICE CHAIN

Earth Observation data and retrieval algorithms, in combination with ocean circulation models and in-situ data, have gradually become an important contributor to improved understanding of the Earth system. EO data provide high resolution and large spatial coverage observations of the sea surface and have made it possible to study dynamic ocean mesoscale processes such as eddies and fronts.

To monitor ocean parameters from space, several different satellite systems and sensors are and will become available in the future. Large-, regional- and meso-scale weather and ocean features can be observed by polar orbiting satellites with sensors operating in a wide part of the electromagnetic wave spectrum. Microwave sensors acquire data independent of sunlight and clouds, and are used to monitor wind, waves, ocean currents, oil spills, and sea ice. Visible and infrared (IR) sensors monitor sea surface temperature, fronts, currents, eddies and ocean colour. Meso and small-scale features such as ocean current patterns, fronts, eddies, surface and internal waves and oil slicks can, under favourable meteorological conditions (normally the wind speed must be in the range 3-11 m/s), be monitored with high-resolution polar orbiting Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) systems. Sea level measurements by satellite radar altimeters (RA) represent relatively low-cost data, which can be used for global mapping for ocean currents as well as for wind speed and wave height. Recent improvements in orbit determinations and geoid modelling, and the availability of overlapping coverage from two radar altimeter satellites can contribute to better estimation of regional currents including eddies, which is required by oil companies operating floating platforms primarily in deep offshore areas.

EO data will be used both in Concept A: Integrated services and in Concept B EO-data specific as defined in Figure 3. The overall system will support services using real time EO data and historical data.

Figure 3. Service concept for the offshore industry market including use of EO data. The model suite composed of the ocean model, the ecosystem model, the sea ice model and the central data assimilation module. Also shown is its interface to input sources and the range of output products with particular emphasis on the service concept for the marine operation market and the boundary and transition between VACs and MOs.

3.2 IN SITU MEASUREMENTS

Present remote sensing techniques do not provide information about the internal variability of the ocean. To probe the interior of the ocean, in situ measurements, such as ADCPs and wave buoys, for accurate and continuously monitoring of local real time ocean current and wave conditions, respectively. Such measurements provide the possibility for long term monitoring in real time, which is essential for design of offshore installations and operations. On the other hand, such measurements only provide vertical profile measurements at a limited number of selected points. It is not possible to produce forecasts based entirely on in situ measurements. In situ data will be used both for real time monitoring and for statistics based on time series.

3.3 OCEAN MODELLING SYSTEMS

The ocean modelling systems aim to provide full three-dimensional oceanographic fields as frequently as the user requires. Model simulations can be made both in hindcast, real time and forecast mode. However, the model results need extensive validation against in situ measurements and EO data. Model validation has significantly improved the skill of model representations of the marine climate and environmental systems over the last decade. The improvement in model systems is also due to increased computational power, the improved parameterisations of non-modelled processes using EO data, and the development of data assimilation techniques. The ocean modelling system to be used in the EMOFOR services is described on more detail in section 4.1 and 5.4.

3.4 INTEGRATED OCEAN MONITORING AND FORECASTING SYSTEM

The data assimilation system is at the core of the integrated ocean monitoring and forecasting system, as it allows for optimally accounting for the information contained in different observing systems such as ocean models, ice models, EO systems and networks of in situ sensors. In such a system the ocean circulation model is used as an engine to provide time series of oceanographic fields by integrating the model state forward in time. EO data and in situ data is assimilated into the system at times where the data is available to adjust the model state to the "real world".

Vital elements of the integrated system are therefore:

- *the availability and quality of in-situ and satellite data,*
- *the "quality" of the selected ocean circulation model*
- *the assimilation scheme including analyses of ocean fields, analyses of residuals in the forcing, initial values, boundary values and parameterisations, as well as error statistics in the mean state and residuals.*

Currently, several regional operational and pre-operational integrated oceanography systems exist or are being implemented. These include: the FOAM and MERCATOR operational systems for the Atlantic, the SOPRANE project for the North-East Atlantic, the Mediterranean Forecasting System Pilot Project (MFSPP), the DIADEM project for the North Atlantic and Nordic Seas and the TOPAZ project for the North Atlantic, Nordic Seas and European coastal zones.

Such integrated numerical models and observing systems produce a large range of information and products such as: monthly ocean current prediction; - and daily to weekly marine sea state, current, storm surges and water quality forecasts. In addition to the quality of the models and assimilation tools, the reliability and utilisation of the products depend upon the quality of the observing systems, telecommunication networks, and rapid information distribution system and services. Established end-users of these products range from commercial customers and governmental

entities to scientific researchers. In EMOFOR the main focus will be to design and implement ocean monitoring and forecasting services, which are optimal for end users in the offshore industry. In EMOFOR the pre-operational ocean model and data assimilation system, DIADEM/TOPAZ, will form the baseline reference. In this model system a physical ocean model, an ecosystem model and a sea ice model are operated in individual or coupled modes. The model grid used in DIADEM/TOPAZ covers the Atlantic Ocean with focus on the North Atlantic region. The ocean model uses atmospheric forcing fields (ECMWF data) for the forward integration, and the model result is used as input to the sea ice model and the ecosystem model. Remote sensing data are currently assimilated every week into the model using EnKF filter, and the model system is also capable of assimilating vertical profiles of in-situ data such as temperature profiles.

The data assimilation module, which combines the observed data fields and the model data, forms the central element of the suite and can be applied to all three models, either individually or in combination. The model suite, developed and implemented by NERSC, produces a series of predictions of 3 dimensional oceanographic fields, such as temperature, salinity and current; marine ecosystem variables and sea ice variables. Both global, regional and local model domains can be selected with accurate bathymetry and land boundaries, and based on a grid generation tool the model domain will also always be defined with best model resolution in the area of particular interest. Moreover, the system introduces a further downscaling capability through nesting high resolution models covering the regional areas of particular interest.

This integrated model and data assimilation system, including EO data and insitu data, will be the core element in the development of monitoring and forecasting services for the offshore industry. Use of EO data will be an important part of the services, both through direct observation of the sea surface and indirectly through assimilation of EO data into the monitoring and forecasting system as illustrated in Figure 3.

4. STATUS OF EXISTING SERVICES TO MARINE OPERATORS

4.1 SERVICES PROVIDED BY FUGRO GEOS

Within the context of the EMOFOR consortium, Fugro GEOS is defined as the market owner. Fugro GEOS has over two decades of experience in the provision of meteorological and oceanographic information to the offshore industry, for monitoring, forecasting, analytical and data storage/dissemination purposes. This experience has led to the development of a wide range of metocean services, aimed at providing clients with all their metocean needs from a single supplier, and to an unrivalled database of clients. The use of EO data in the activities of Fugro GEOS is a more recent development, but as the offshore industry moves into increasingly challenging areas EO data are becoming an integral part of Fugro GEOS' service portfolio.

4.1.1 In situ measurements

Direct measurement of the metocean environment is a core Fugro GEOS business activity, undertaken world-wide to support the design, implementation and operation of marine engineering and development projects, including fixed and floating oil and gas production systems, submarine pipelines and cables and industrial and municipal coastal facilities. Measurement programmes are

devised and conducted to suit a range of purposes, from long term instrument deployments in support of infrastructure design, to rapid turnaround 'look-see' projects. Parameters measured include winds, waves, currents, water levels, tides and seawater characteristics such as temperature and salinity.

Innovative approaches to current measurement include:

- 'RIGADCP', a rig-based real-time display of currents through the water column. Included in this package is a current forecast functionality, which produces forecast time series of tidal and non-tidal currents.
- The Towed-ADCP system, which is towed by a vessel away from the rig with the measurements viewed in real-time aboard the towing vessel. This system is used to measure, for example, the currents associated with warm-core eddies from the North Brazil Current, from which assessments can be made of their likely impact on the offshore activities in the Trinidad region.

Deliverables from measurement programmes are either data reports or more detailed documents containing design and operating criteria and oceanographic analyses. Fugro GEOS has also initiated major speculative current measurement studies in the North-east Atlantic (Atlantic Margin Metocean Project) and in the Gulf of Mexico the Gulf Lower Layer (GULL) study to investigate the occurrence of severe near-bed currents.

4.1.2 Real-time Monitoring

Fugro GEOS designs, installs and maintains reliable real-time measurement systems to monitor meteorological and oceanographic conditions. A flexible, web-based real-time data display system has been developed to display data from a broad range of instrumentation over small or large networks. A typical example is the METNET system (further described in D3) covering Shell's North Sea platforms.

4.1.3 Metocean Consultancy

Fugro GEOS' Seadata division specialises in the provision of detailed, expert oceanographic advice in support of a wide range of activities in the offshore industry, including exploration rig selection, production platform design and operability, pipeline design and tow route conditions. These studies integrate, analyse and interpret data from measurements, models and, increasingly, satellites to produce detailed design and operating criteria and in-depth appraisals of metocean conditions around the world.

Fugro GEOS has recently developed a downtime appraisal service, which provides seismic and other offshore operators with a rapid (24-hour turnaround) site specific analysis of wind and wave conditions for operability assessment. The downtime products are based on SAR and altimeter data available to registered users across the internet. The service deliverable is a report that in addition to the wind and wave tables and presentations also summarises, from public domain literature, the circulation of the region of interest and gives brief details of key processes of interest.

From its Houston offices, Fugro GEOS operates the Trinidad Ring Advisory Co-operative (TRAC), which provides weekly reports to participating oil companies on the size and movement of the

warm-core eddies, based on sea-surface height altimeter measurements and surface drifter trajectories.

4.1.4 Offshore Weather Forecasting

Fugro GEOS operates a weather forecasting service for the offshore industry from offices in Abu Dhabi, Kuala Lumpur and Singapore. Detailed assessments of wind, wave and swell conditions are available for any location in the world, although the specific focus of the service is on the Middle East, South-east Asia, the Mediterranean, West Africa and the Indian Ocean.

4.1.5 Metocean Modelling

Regional and basin scale circulation modelling services are provided through Ocean Numerics, a joint venture between Fugro GEOS and the Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Centre (NERSC). Chapter 4.3.1 and 5.4 of this document gives more details of the model development work undertaken by NERSC and Ocean Numerics.

4.2 SERVICES PROVIDED BY CLS

4.2.1 Altimetry products

CLS has a long experience in the processing, validation, distribution and exploitation of satellite altimeter data (TOPEX/POSEIDON, ERS-1/2 and GEOSAT Follow On and soon Jason-1 and ENVISAT). At the beginning of 1997, the CLS capability in near real time processing of altimeter data was developed as part of DUACS (Developing Use of Altimetry for Climate Studies), a 3-year European Commission Project. The DUACS project has demonstrated that altimeter data can be processed in near real time with sufficient accuracy to improve the skill of climate simulations and, more specially, seasonal climate forecasts. During the project CLS prepared Homogeneous Historical (HH) altimeter products and Near Real Time (NRT) altimeter products for the DUACS partners. The NRT and HH products developed and refined during DUACS are now developing further in the DUACS Follow On project and are widely used by the scientific community. Now, this project continues to serve operational oceanography users as part of AVISO, a service designed by the CNES (French Spatial Agency) and CLS. AVISO provides user services and altimetry support from ground support facilities for controlling the DORIS and Poseidon instruments, for processing data from DORIS and the T/P, Jason-1 and Envisat-1 altimeters. HH altimeter products are a long time series of multi-satellite altimetric data using the most accurate data sets available. They include TOPEX/POSEIDON (T/P), ERS-1 and ERS-2 data, and soon GFO. They are obtained from delayed time and precise data sets T/P GDRs and ERS-1/2 OPRs).

The current products consist of:

- along-track CORrected Sea Surface Height (CORSSH) files (one by cycle),
- along-track Sea Level Anomaly (SLA) files (one per year),
- maps of Sea Level Anomalies (MSLA) (one map every 7 days, see Fig. 4).

The operational project weekly delivers NRT high-resolution products for multiple satellites (T/P, ERS, Jason, GFO, and soon ENVISAT). The acquisition uses DORIS precise real time orbits. They are updated every week with a time delay between 48 and 72 hours.

NRT products are:

- along-track Sea Level Anomaly (SLA) files (one per week and per satellite),

- maps of Sea Level Anomalies (MSLA) (one map every week).
- The data cover a large spectrum of operational oceanography needs, from mesoscale to climate applications. They are used in particular for
- climate prediction,
 - operational oceanography,
 - oceanographic research cruises,
 - fisheries,
 - offshore industry.

Figure 4. Global map of Sea level anomalies computed by CLS. The map is obtained using an improved space/time objective analysis method improving long wavelength errors.

Nowadays, altimeter measurements represent a major source of information to describe the present state of the global ocean. As such, altimeter data are currently assimilated in most (if not all) ocean forecast models and coupled ocean-atmosphere models used for predicting climate evolution.

Commercial applications of altimeter-derived sea level information is quite recent and essentially based on operational delivery of near-real-time information concerning sea level anomalies and associated currents, as shown in Figure 5. For offshore oil industry such products are useful to establish current climatologies in prospective drilling area and to monitor currents in real-time at exploration sites.

Figure 5. Sea level anomalies and associated current computed by CLS based on ERS-2 RA fast delivery products and Topex-Poseidon Interim Geophysical data. The example above is in the Socotra Island area in the western Indian Ocean.

4.2.2 Operational oceanography systems

The data provided by DUACS are used in particular in operational oceanography systems. CLS is also involved in the development of these systems such as:

- SOAP, the mesoscale oceanic forecast system of the French Navy which assimilate altimetric data in the Northeast Atlantic areas;
- DIADEM/TOPAZ, an advanced data assimilation system for a coupled primitive equation ocean circulation and marine ecosystem model for the North Atlantic and the Nordic Seas with enhanced resolution in the European coastal zones;
- MFS the Mediterranean Forecasting System where the objective is to set up and test a near real time acquisition and processing system of remote sensing data for the Mediterranean Sea;

- MERCATOR project, which delivers bulletins by bringing a continuous three dimensional picture of the ocean and offers forecasts for the next two weeks, based on archive and real-time data.

The MERCATOR project is the French contribution to the international program GODAE (Global Ocean Data Assimilation Experiment). GODAE is a practical demonstration of real-time global ocean data assimilation in order to provide a regular, complete depiction of the ocean circulation at time scales of a few days, space scales of several tens of kilometres, and consistent with a set of space and direct measurements and appropriate dynamical and physical constraints. The GODAE purpose consists of a global and integrated approach combining model, in-situ and remote sensing data through data assimilation. This approach will be highly beneficial to the development of operational oceanography applications by providing a new set of products.

4.2.3 Fishery services

In 1999, CLS and THALOS combined their experience and expertise to offer an easy-to-use, onboard oceanographic data service for the fishing community: CATSAT. Ocean-observing satellites and marine meteorology can help fishermen to:

- locate favourable fishing grounds,
- reduce operating costs,
- improve safety during fishing operations,
- meet their quotas more efficiently.

CATSAT offers oceanographic data acquired by satellites and marine meteorology data, including:

- altimetry/sea level anomaly maps (SLA) from DUACS,
- weather forecasts from ECMWF,
- sea surface temperature from NOAA AVHRR satellites, see Fig. 6
- ocean colour from satellite Vegetation

4.2.4 Tidal model products

A finite element tide model maintained and distributed by CLS provides the tidal elevation on each point of the global ocean. Based on the harmonic theory of tides, the 27 main tidal constituents were computed (M_2 , S_2 , K_1 , O_1 ...). A specific prediction algorithm was developed to compute tidal time series from the tidal constituents. Barotropic tide currents can be deduced from this model (Fig. 7).

Figure 6: Sea surface temperature provided by CATSAT (Arabian Sea)

Thanks to the finite element technique, if a specific study is needed to regionally improve the accuracy of tidal solutions over a difficult area, a local high-resolution version of the tide model can easily be embedded in the global model. Regional enhancement of the model resolution and accuracy has already been successfully tested in several areas.

This tidal model is used in various applications:

- tide prediction software SHOMAR of the French Navy,
- coastal or shelf areas studies, the extraction of these global tide solutions provide tidal boundary conditions for local models,
- calibration of satellites (TOPEX/ POSEIDON, ERS-1, ERS-2, and soon ENVISAT),
- bathymetric surveys where the prediction of the sea level due to tides allows a better calibration of measured depths,

Figure 7. Barotropic tidal currents extracted from a local model version of the global finite element model (Faroes and Shetland area, M2 tide component).

4.3 SERVICES PROVIDED BY NERSC

The strategy of the research and service development at NERSC is based on an integrated approach using information from various sources combined with numerical model simulations and advanced data assimilation techniques. This implies that earth observation methods are used in combination with *in situ* field observations and numerical models. Based on these three fundamental methodologies a pre-operational ocean monitoring and forecasting system has been developed within a large number of national- and EU- funded projects. The system is continuously undergoing further extension in order to include assimilation of an increasing number of available EO data and *in situ* measurements. Another important activity within the above framework is to develop new and refined algorithms for parameterisation of existing and new EO data, which are consistent with the interface to the modelling and assimilation system. Products and services from NERSC is defined by the integrated output from this advanced ocean monitoring and forecasting system.

4.3.1 Ocean modelling and forecasting services

The ocean modelling and forecasting system consists of the following major components:

The **Hybrid Coordinate Ocean Model (HYCOM)** (including model grids, bathymetry, ocean model, nesting and tidal boundary conditions), a modified Hibler **sea ice model**, a **biochemical model** and **assimilation techniques**. This system, which is presently running in close to real time for the North Atlantic in the TOPAZ/DIADEM project, is forced via ECMWF-atmospheric data. Sea Surface Temperature (SST) and Sea Level Anomaly (SLA) data from satellites are assimilated weekly using the Ensemble Kalman Filter (EnKF). This system also offers the opportunity to assimilate sea surface salinity, ice concentration and ice thickness, and vertical temperature and salinity profiles.

The horizontal grid in the model system uses conformal mapping to define a new spherical coordinate system with the poles placed at user specified locations. This allows for fairly general model grids and for focusing horizontal resolution in the chosen regions. The currently ongoing large scale real time experiment in TOPAZ has a variable resolution with approximately 15-20 km grid cells in the Gulf Stream extension and with a generally coarser grid moving into the South Atlantic and Arctic Sea (Figure 8). The model system allows for nesting. In order to provide services for the oil industry an intermediate model has been defined for an area including all of the North Sea and the Atlantic Margin, using a model resolution of 7 km. However, a resolution down to 2 km is required to capture the typical mesoscale variability in the region of interest. Such a high resolution model has been established for an area covering the shelf slopes in the North Sea, including the Faeroes. This is referred to as the NWAG model and is being used in hindcast mode by the oil industry for developing a data base for currents to support design and operating criteria. The technique of nesting is general and is "easily" performed for other selected geographical areas.

For every defined ocean model integration time step the ocean model provides the ocean states for each grid cell (i,j) i.e. the layer thicknesses (for up to 22 layers at each location in the TOPAZ system), temperature, salinity, barotropic pressure, barotropic current components (U,V), and baroclinic current components (U,V) at each of the 22 depths. The model results (three dimensional oceanographic fields) from the TOPAZ/DIADEM system and the nested ocean model domains are usually displayed every six hours, but can be displayed for selected geographical regions every hour. The physics of the ocean described by the model output from HYCOM are used to generate ensembles used as input to the assimilation scheme to force a sea ice model, which provides sea ice parameters such as concentration, extent and sea ice thickness. The sea ice model provides important feedback to the ocean circulation model.

Satellite remote sensing of the sea surface is currently the main source of ocean data for assimilation into ocean modelling systems system using the Ensemble Kalman Filter. The satellites provide sea surface temperatures, sea level anomalies and ocean colour data. However, the subsurface and deep ocean cannot be observed by satellite remote sensing techniques, since all electromagnetic waves are rapidly damped out in water. Methods for assimilating vertical profiles of standard oceanographic high accuracy point measurements from moored or drifting buoys has recently been developed and implemented into the DIADEM/TOPAZ system.

Earth Observation data which are assimilated in this system include sea surface temperature, sea surface height, near surface wind field, chlorophyll-a concentration and distribution, and sea ice concentration. The EO data come from the currently operating satellites (i.e. ERS-2, TOPEX/POSEIDON, NOAA TIROS, DMSP, OrbView-2, QuickSCAT, ADEOS-2).

a)

b)

Figure 8. a) the model domain and grid used in the TOPAZ/DIADEM model; b) Sea surface temperature and ice concentration from the ocean monitoring and forecasting system. The method of nested ocean modelling for the NWAG project is shown in the plot on the right indicating the location.

Service cycle

The present cycle of delivery services at NERSC are now described. Every week the pre-operational ocean monitoring and forecasting system provides the following products:

- Analysed oceanographic fields and statistics for the day of data delivery
- 7 day forecast and statistics (100 ensembles) of oceanographic fields
- 14 day forecast of mean oceanographic fields (mean of the ensembles are generated and integrated forward in time)

On the analysis day the 100 ensembles from last week 7 days integration is run through a EnKF filter along with EO data (and in the near future in situ data as well) to get the best estimate of the present ocean state (analysed oceanographic fields). The resulting analysed oceanographic fields consists of 100 model states (ensembles), which thereafter are integrated one week forward in time to provide the 7 day forecast. This forecast is then used in the next week analysis along with available observed data. Furthermore, the mean ocean state is calculated from the ensembles, which again is integrated 7 more days forward in time providing a 14 day forecast. The real time experiment cycle is described in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Flow diagram showing the analysis process and the delivery time scale of the ocean modelling products. Keep in mind that the delivery time scale of forecasts in real time depend strongly on the capacity of the computer used, and the rate/amount of data available for assimilation

The model results (all the oceanographic parameters including current) are presented as horizontal contour plots, as vertical sections of the parameters or as time series of the parameter at a point. Examples of data presentation are provided in Figure 10. Furthermore the system also provides statistical analysis (mean, variances, covariance, correlation's) of the ensembles with respect to the oceanographic parameters included in the model result file.

Figure 10. Example of model output from the DIADEM/TOPAZ system. Plot A shows the model area with a line indicating a section line for which the model system provides vertical sections of temperature and salinity similar to the salinity plot in Plot C and Plot D (covering a smaller part of the section line). Plot B shows a blow up of the area within the red box in Plot A. The surface current is overlaid on the surface temperature plot. All plots of ocean parameters are for the 2nd week of February 1996.

4.3.2 SAR observations of eddies and fronts

Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) monitoring of eddies and current features has been developed for the deep exploration off Mid-Norway (Fig. 11). The metocean conditions of these areas can be extreme because of the exposure to the Atlantic Ocean and the Norwegian Sea. SAR observations of surface current patterns has been used as one of several methods to obtain knowledge about current conditions required for design and operation of floating structures in this region. Also the use of satellite altimetry was a part of the observation programme in this project.

The region's complicated bathymetry, combined with strong ocean currents and presence of a front between Norwegian Atlantic Current and the Norwegian Coastal Current makes it an area of high mesoscale variability, with generation of meanders and eddies representing the maximum current velocities. Hence, regular monitoring over an extended period of time was necessary to obtain reliable statistics on the current regime, including mesoscale eddy activity.

SAR images from the European Space Agency's ERS-2 satellite have been used to map the location of fronts and eddies and their characteristic scale and rotation in the study area (Figure 10). Eddies were observed in about 75 % of the SAR images, which covered a period of about 18 months. The typical horizontal scale of the eddies was 10-30 km and the rotation was cyclonic for most of the eddies. In one case the mean propagation speed over a 3-day period was estimated to be 18 cm/s for one cyclonic eddy. Comparison of satellite observed features with bottom topography showed that the maximum occurrence of fronts and eddies was found along the shelf break from 62.5° N to 65° N and from 66.5° N to 67.5° N. This area coincides with the core of the NorthAtlantic Current as observed by a moored current meter array.

The SAR method will be implemented as part of the eddy monitoring service, where altimeter, IR and optical images are used as input data. SAR images will be most useful in areas of frequent cloud cover where optical and IR images provide little or no information, and where altimeter products have limited capability to capture eddies. Northwest Europe is an example of a region where SAR is expected to be useful. In the Gulf of Mexico, altimetry combined with IR and optical images, will probably be sufficient to track the eddies.

Figure 11 (a) Map of the eddy area west of Mid-Norway where the squares indicate location of ERS-2 SAR scenes used in the eddy mapping project. The bold rectangle shows location of the image in b; (b) ERS-2 SAR image covering the Ormen Lange field, obtained on 22 April 1998, showing intense eddy activity. One predominant cyclonic eddy is marked by the red circle. ©ESA/TSS, 1998, and (c) graphical presentation of the eddy position and propagation observed in a sequence of SAR images.

5. EMOFOR SERVICE DEFINITION

5.1 A SERVICE SYSTEM WITH THREE MODES

The EMOFOR service system will consist of three service modes which will be activated according to the requirements from the operators. Based on the requirements defined by Fugro GEOS the service system is defined to be operated in the following modes:

- Monitoring mode (real-time or near real time),
- hindcast mode (met-ocean statistics from time series of model simulations as well as observations)
- forecasting mode.

The elements of the service system including information flow are shown in Fig.12 and the main components of the service are summarised in Table 4. The service will consist of four main components: Eddy mapping and tracking with EO data (monitoring mode), eddy statistics from altimeter data (hindcast mode), statistics on currents from model data (hindcast mode), and current forecasting from models (forecasting mode).

Figure 12. Overview of the main components of the proposed metocean service for offshore industry. Each of the boxes will contain modules for processing specific types of data and running the models required for the area where the service will be implemented.

5.1.1 Input data

The first category of input data to the service consists of four types of satellite data: i) altimetric current products for eddy mapping and gridded SLA fields for use in modelling (described in 4.2),

ii) SAR images analysed for eddies (described in 5.2), iii) infrared images analysed for eddy detection by contrast in SST and composed into gridded SST fields for use in modelling, and iv) optical images analysed for eddy detection by contrast in ocean colour. The second category of input data is in situ measurements of currents by ADCP or other instruments mounted on deepwater rigs. In situ measurements are site specific data which provides profiles of currents for the water column in realtime for the operators.. These data are also used for validation of satellite-derived eddy maps and model simulations. Atmospheric fields are used to provide weather and wave forecasts as well as to deliver forcing fields for the ocean models. The ocean climatology data are used for tuning/validation of the ocean models.

5.1.2 Data processing and modelling

After reception of low level satellite data products from the data providers, geophysical parameters are retrieved, features such as eddies are identified, gridded fields are compiled by averaging data over time (i.e. one week), and other statistical estimates are retrieved from analysis of time series of data. This processing feeds information into the monitoring mode as well as to the ocean current model simulations. The model system consists of the large-scale Atlantic-Arctic model nested to high-resolution models over smaller areas, as described in 4.3.1. Other models such as tidal models and coupled ice-ocean models are also available for use in the services. The modelling activity including data assimilation is described in more detail in section 5.4.

5.1.3 Output products

The output of the service is a number of information products divided in three modes (Monitoring mode, Hindcast mode and Forecasting mode) according to the user requirements (Table 4).

Table 4. Service components and modes

Service components	Components of a 3-D service system			Service modes		
	2-D sea surface maps from EO data	In situ data: surface and vertical profile	3-D ocean field from models	Monitoring (real time)	Hindcast (analysis of time series)	Forecasting (1 – 7 days)
1 Eddy mapping and tracking with EO data	X	v		X		
2 Eddy statistics from altimeter hindcast data	X	v			X	
3 Statistics from model hindcast data		v	X		X	
4 Forecasting from models		v	X			X

X: main role of service

V: in situ data are independent elements of the service, but are also important for validation of EO products as well as model simulations.

Each service mode will be implemented through four service components: 1) Eddy tracking with EO data, 2) Eddy statistics from altimeter hindcast, 3) Statistics from model hindcast data, and 4) forecasting from ocean circulation models. The service components and modes are described in more detail in the next section.

5.2 INTEGRATED SERVICES TO BE PROVIDED BY FUGRO GEOS

5.2.1 Service modes

The *Monitoring Mode* is currently the most important part of the met-ocean services provided by Fugro GEOS to the offshore industry, where measurements of currents, wind, waves, etc. are carried out in real time onboard a platform. The monitoring methods include use of drifters deployed in eddies transmitting positions via ARGOS. The position data from the buoys are used to map the propagation and orbital speed of an eddy. The drift data are used in combination with altimeter SLA maps (Fig. 13). This method has been used for some of the large warm-core eddies (rings) associated with the North Brazil Current.

SHA contours (cm) for the two rings for 03 December (based on data collected for 28 November - 08 December 1999) and three TRAC drifter paths up to 09 December 1999 (red-18751, green-4688, blue-4689).

Figure 14. a) Use of downward-looking ADCP mounted on a rig to monitor current profiles below the rig down to 500 m depth; b) Example of ADCP current data displayed in real-time.

Onboard a platform the most important method for monitoring currents is the ADCP (Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler) which provides real-time profiles of currents from surface to a depth of typically 500m. Data from ADCPs are plotted and listed onboard a platform as shown in Fig. 14.

The Monitoring Mode will include use of EO data as the major data source of the service, where altimeter data, SAR images and optical/IR images all can contribute to the observation and tracking of eddies.

The **Hindcast Mode**, using high resolution models, is normally carried out as part of the exploration/appraisal and engineering design phases of an offshore development. The model simulations, which typically run for one year, provides an extensive set of data on all oceanographic variables, and statistics of these parameters can be retrieved from the model data. The model data are usually compared with in situ measurements prior to such statistical analysis, as part of the model validation.

The **Forecasting Mode** is used during the installation and production phases to ensure safe operations and avoid dangerous situations, which can arise as result of extreme currents. The forecasting is done by assessing in situ observations combined with analysis of EO data and model results by experts. Example of site-specific forecasting is shown in Fig. 15 where current measurements by ADCP is extrapolated for the next 24 hours. Use of high-resolution models in forecasting will provide a much better quantitative estimation of currents on regional scale. This forecasting method has only recently been developed and will be further described in section 5.4..

Figure 15. Site-specific forecasting of currents using extrapolation of measurements from an ADCP

Services using EO data as the major source of information are under development by CLS and NERSC, as described in section 5.3 and 5.4. Some EO products, such as SLA maps from altimeter,

have already been used by Fugro GEOS as shown in Fig. 14. The usefulness of EO data is enhanced when used in combination with other information from models, in situ data and other available data sources. Even if ENVISAT SAR data will have better spatial and temporal coverage than ERS, there will still be significant gaps between repeated passes, and tracking features from day to day will still be difficult if we only use SAR data. By combining altimeter, SAR, infrared radiometer and optical images, data will be available more frequently the eddy mapping capability is improved and the reliability of the service is enhanced. Furthermore, the integration of EO monitoring methods with modelling and other observation techniques will be of importance to meet user requirements for regular monitoring and forecasting.

5.2.2 Service Organisation

In order to deliver an integrated EMOFOR service, a clear definition of functional responsibility for the service chain elements is necessary. The role of Fugro GEOS, CLS and NERSC to provide the various elements of the service is shown in Figure 16.

Figure 16. Functional responsibilities of EMOFOR project partners

Fugro GEOS will have the overall responsibility to deliver the service products to the customers, CLS and NERSC have important roles to provide several products to Fugro GEOS. A potential blockage in the service chain is the formatting of the various data types that will be integrated into the EMOFOR products. The architecture of the data warehouse will have to be compatible with the

EO data, model data and in-situ data types. It may be necessary or more efficient for NERSC and CLS to undertake some additional formatting prior to transfer of their service elements. This is a major issue that will require detailed discussion between the project partners and Fugro GEOS IT staff, but such discussions would also hopefully resolve any data mis-match issues that may arise.

Reliability is a critical requirement of the service. If products are delivered late, incomplete or erratically, the offshore industry will not regard it as indispensable to operational decision-making. All partners will therefore have to ensure that some contingency is in place to ensure a seamless service in the event of unforeseen circumstances preventing normal delivery.

5.3 DESCRIPTION OF SERVICE ELEMENTS PROVIDED BY CLS

Concerning the upgrade of the EO service chain to exploit ENVISAT data, CLS will take charge of the exploitation of the following data:

- RA-2 processing and dissemination;
- MERIS/AATSR processing and dissemination for ocean and ice features in co-operation with the NERSC

To switch from pre-operational T/P ERS era to fully operational ENVISAT-JASON period, CLS will develop a completely new upgraded version of the DUACS data merging software that will operate under UNIX. Its main outputs will be:

- High quality sea level anomalies (SLA),
- High quality along tracks mapped on a regular grid (MSLA).

At the present time, the nominal operating frequency of DUACS delivery is once per week but it could be produced at a higher frequency if needed. The DUACS software will be able to combine data from several satellites. Indeed ENVISAT RA-2 will replace the ERS altimeter and in combination with Jason (to replace T/P) and GFO, the altimeter coverage and repeat cycles will be optimum for monitoring the sea surface height variability associated with mesoscale and large scale time dependent ocean circulation features.

To fulfil the needs of offshore applications, CLS will provide new services with an adapted operational interface based on the ENVISAT and other available satellite altimeter measurements. These new services include an “eddy-tracking” service, which will use an automatic eddy and front detection method studied in CLS that will be operationally implemented (altimeter data, sea surface temperature and ocean colour maps will be merged together).

This new service will be designed so that they can be used in near real time.

5.4 DESCRIPTION OF SERVICE ELEMENTS PROVIDED BY NERSC

NERSC will provide the following resources to EMOFOR

- The latest generation ocean models and data assimilation techniques
- NERSC is a partner in a new state of the art super computer system being installed at Parallax, University in Bergen, in December 2001. The system is an IBM power4, 500 Giga flops machine having 96 CPUs, each with a peak performance of 5.2 Gigaflops. NERSC has priority access to a share of this system, which will be used to support general computing needs at NERSC including the model and data assimilation simulations needed in the project.

The services provided by the pre-operational DIADEM/TOPAZ system will provide nesting conditions for the high resolution model to be set up in specific regions where Fugro GEOS is performing ocean monitoring activities with in situ current measurements. Profiles of ADCP data will be compared to the high resolution model in order to monitor and predict eddies, which are propagating towards floating structures and can be a severe risk factor for these structures. Oceanographic fields from satellite data (SLA and SST) provided by CLS will be assimilated into the model system but now with data also from ENVISAT. The operational scheme for the intended forecasting services will be similar to the DIADEM/TOPAZ cycle illustrated in Figure 9. NERSC will offer the possibility of operating the model and assimilation system in three different modes as shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Modes of modelling services provided by NERSC

<i>Hindcast mode</i>	<i>To offer detailed statistical information (space and time) about the oceanographic condition in the selected region.</i>
<i>Real time mode</i>	<i>Support the monitoring by providing analysed oceanographic fields combining EO data, in situ observations and model calculations in an optimal way using advanced assimilation</i>
<i>Forecast mode</i>	<i>Integrate the analysed field forward in time to provide 7 days and a 14 days mean forecast</i>

Furthermore, NERSC will contribute to the eddy tracking service proposed by CLS, by incorporating ENVISAT ASAR data. This component of an integrated service will be similar to the SAR monitoring service demonstrated for Mid-Norway. Optimal modes for ASAR observations of eddies and current patterns will be investigated for areas where such features are important and Fugro GEOS has ongoing field programmes. With use of ASAR wid swath mode (400 km wide swath) it will be possible to observe a given site more frequently than what could be done by ERS SAR (100 km swath). The observation frequency is also dependent on latitude and occurrence of favourable wind conditions. By combining the use of ASAR with optical and IR images as well as altimeter data, we plan to provide a better eddy tracking service where ENVISAT data play an important role. The eddy tracking service will be used as a complement to the modelling and forecasting service provided by the DIADEM/TOPAZ system and the in situ observations provided by Fugro GEOS.

5.5 SUMMARY OF SERVICE COMPONENTS AND CAPABILITY

Service components	<i>Eddy mapping and tracking with EO data</i>	<i>Eddy statistics from altimeter hindcast data</i>	<i>Current statistics from model hindcast data</i>	<i>Forecasting from models</i>
Main product	Maps of eddies in specific regions	Eddy kinetic energy maps: mean, seasonal , monthly	3-D current fields from model simulations for a given period	Forecasted current and other oceanographical fields: 1 – 7 days
Near real time or offline	Near real time (within 1 – 2 days)	Offline	Offline	Near real time
Use of EO data	Altimeter, SAR, infrared radiometer, optical images	Altimeter data obtained over the last 10 years	SST and SLA fields	SST and SLA fields
Which satellites	JASON, ENVISAT, NOAA, etc.	Topex/Poseidon, ERS-1/-2	Topex/Poseidon, NOAA, ERS-1/-2	JASON, ENVISAT, NOAA, etc.
Use of <i>in situ</i> current measurements	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Other input data	no	no	Atmospheric forcing fields and ocean climate data	Atmospheric forcing fields and ocean climate data
Product interval	3 – 6 days	As agreed with customer	As agreed with customer	weekly
Product format	Maps in standard format agreed with customer	Maps in standard format agreed with customer	Plots and tabular presentations of current statistics at specific sites	Plots and tabular presentations of current forecasts at specific sites
Product size	≈ 10 – 100 kbyte	≈ 10 – 100 kbyte	≈ 10 – 100 kbyte	≈ 10 – 100 kbyte
Transmission to customers	Attachment to e-mail	Attachment to e-mail	Attachment to e-mail	Attachment to e-mail
Service chain established	Yes by CLS for SLA, SST and ocean colour products, by NERSC for SAR	Yes, by CLS	Yes, by NERSC	Yes, by NERSC
Areas where services will be available in 2003	Global, focus on Northwest Europe, Gulf of Mexico	Global, under satellite tracks (latitude ~+/- 75°)	Atlantic Ocean	Gulf of Mexico

6. CONCLUDING REMARKS

This document has defined the main components and functionalities of the EMOFOR service chain targeting the deepwater offshore operation market. The background for the services are described where current monitoring and forecasting capabilities have been developed by a number nationally and EU-funded projects coordinated through EuroGOOS. The planned service components are based on user requirements for current monitoring and forecasting in areas where strong currents due to eddies are critical factors in various stages of offshore developments. The service components are based on existing EO data products and modelling capability offered by CLS and NERSC. Fugro GEOS will include the services offered by CLS and NERSC to expand their existing monitoring services for the global offshore market.

A more detailed description of the service components and plan for service trials are described in report D3: Action plan for implementation of the services. This document also identifies critical barriers to be resolved and actions to be taken before the services can become operational.

A market analysis for the EMOFOR services is described in the D2 document, Consolidated Business Plan. This document will be upgraded to become the D10 document, including cost analysis and price estimates for the service by November 2002.